

The Egyptian Hieroglyph of the Crested Ibis, from the Cheops' pyramid (Akhet Khufu) to the Akhenaten's Glory of Aten

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The name of the Cheops' pyramid, Akhet Khufu, is generally translated as the 'Khufu's horizon'. It is necessary to stress that 'Akhet', in the name of Khufu's pyramid, is written with the hieroglyph of the crested ibis Akh, G25 of Gardiner's list, which means 'spirit'. It is not written with the symbol of the 'sun on horizon', N27 of Gardiner's list. This is clearly shown by the papyri discovered in 2013 at Wady al-Jarf. These papyri are contemporary of Khufu's reign. Even after the evidence of these papyri, Akhet Khufu continues to be rendered as 'Khufu's horizon'. Other interpretations of the term 'Akhet' exist. For instance, the use of Akhet written with the crested ibis is attested in a King Pepi II letter to his vizier Herkhuf, three centuries after Khufu, to indicate the land of the Horizon Dwellers. Schiaparelli, 1892, translated as the land of the 'Spiriti Beati'. We will show further examples of the use of the crested ibis Akh, beyond the name of Khufu' pyramid and the land mentioned by Pepi II. We will consider also the name of Akhenaton, where the crested ibis persists to indicate the 'glory'. The presence of this word is shown by Schiaparelli in Pepi II's letter. In the name of Akhetaten, the city of Akhenaton, we find a true 'horizon', that of the Sun Disk, the sun as a physical object.

This work is proposed as a supplement to my <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407>, proposed in arXiv, due to presence, in the e-print archive, of papers regarding the Cheops (Khufu) pyramid, where Akhet is linked to the wrong sign N27.

Reddit - [Reddit Question](#): "We know that the ancient Egyptians called the great pyramid "Akhet Khufu" (Horizon of Khufu), but how did we know this? How did the name Akhet Khufu become associated with the great pyramid?"

User *BetaKeyTakeaway*: "A mortuary cult was established for the deceased pharaoh, which was practiced in the temples of the Great pyramid. The cemeteries around the pyramid have tombs of people involved in that cult, for instance "Overseer of the Scribes of the Pyramid Akhet-Khufu" or "supervisor of funerary priests of Akhet-Khufu".

User *usuluh*: "Akhet Khufu is also mentioned multiple times in the Wadi Jarf Papyri (A,B,C,D). The radiocarbon dating coincides with the timeline reconstructed from other primary sources, as well as with the organic mortar samples collected from the Great Pyramid's core in two occasions (analyzed in 1985, 1995 and reanalyzed in 2009). These papyri describe transporting white limestone from Tura to the Akhet Khufu Btw. Akhet as a term does not only mean Horizon, but it also refers to the transformation of the deceased into Akh (the spirit), which was believed to travel to the afterlife. This same term is used in other tomb names as well, such as Akhet-Mehu (Giza Tomb: G 2375)".

Here a link to [Akhetmehu tomb](#).

In *usuluh*'s answer, it is mentioned a book by Miroslav Verner, 2015. It is strictly necessary to verify this reference. Besides radiocarbon dating, let us stress that the port of Wadi al-Jarf was created and used under Khufu's reign: "used to store dismantled boats after the expeditions that were regularly led to transfer copper and stones from Sinai to the Nile valley, the galleries featured an elaborate closure system which made use of large and heavy limestone blocks inscribed with the name of Cheops (about 2650 BC)" (April 12, 2013, [Rossella Lorenzi, mentioning Pierre Tallet](#)).

About the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, see <https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.08061>

Akhet Khufu - It is very important to stress that the Akhet in Akhet Khufu is written with the crested ibis, Gardiner G25,

	G25 U+1315C	northern bald ibis	Be effective, effective (Akh) spirit (?h)
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and not with Gardiner N27.

N27	 U+1320C	sun rising over mountain	"horizon"	
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The name "Akhet Khufu" is present in the Wadi al-Jarf papyri. In my article, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2411.08061>, the reader can understand the fundamental importance of the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, discovered by Pierre Tallet in 2013 (Tallet, 2017). **The papyri are of Khufu's time.** Please consider the article by Daniel Weiss, 2022, [Archaeology Magazine](#). "The papyri discovered at Wadi al-Jarf offer revealing clues to the layout of the Giza Plateau and its maritime infrastructure during the period of the pyramid's construction. In the papyri, when Inspector Merer and his men are described approaching the plateau with a boatful of limestone blocks, they pass through the Ro-She Khufu (Mouth of the Lake of Khufu) into either the She Khufu (Lake of Khufu) or the She Akhet Khufu (Lake of the Horizon of Khufu). According to Egyptologist Mark Lehner, director of Ancient Egypt Research Associates, who has led excavations at the Giza Plateau for three decades, this supports scholars' theory that the ancient Egyptians built a network of artificial basins that allowed heavily laden boats to deposit their cargo at the plateau's edge, facilitating the delivery of materials necessary to construct the pyramid".

To have a picture of Akhet Khufu, Ro-She Khufu and She Akhet Khufu, see please the

[PICTURE](#) archived [HERE](#)

This was **the Khufu's project**, that of having Khufu's artificial basins and waterways to support the building of the pyramid. Of the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, SEE PLEASE the PAPHYRUS at the-past.com and note the AKHET below the Khufu's cartouche. Akhet is written with the **crested ibis** (G25, not N27!)

Here Figure 2 in <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2411.08061> :

Fig.1.

And here again the link to the [picture](#), in the article “Records of the pyramid builders: discovering eye-witness accounts of a legendary construction project”, [The Past.](#), 2023. The image is a courtesy of Pierre Tallet, who discovered the papyri.

This is the AKHET that KHUFU knew, AKHET with the CRESTED IBIS; not the horizon with a disk between two hills. Note the symbol of the pyramid.

Pierre Tallet’s articles

In the Figure 1, I am showing one of the many ‘Akhet Khufu’ we can find in the Diary of Merer, “The Diary of Merer (also known as Papyrus Jarf) is the name for papyrus logbooks written over 4,500 years ago by Merer, a middle-ranking official with the title inspector (shꜥ, sehedj). They are the oldest known papyri with text, dating to the 26th year of the reign of Pharaoh Khufu (reigned in the early 26th century BC, estimated c. 2589 – c. 2566 BC) during the Fourth Dynasty of Egypt. The text, written with (hieratic) hieroglyphs, mostly consists of lists of the daily activities of Merer and his crew. The best preserved sections (Papyrus Jarf A and B) document the transportation of white limestone blocks from the Tura quarries to Giza by boat” ([Wikipedia](#), see please references therein).

The Khufu’s arbor and the papyri had been discovered by Tallet and Marouard, 2014. The Diary of Merer has been studied by Pierre Tallet. Let us consider the Tallet’s article entitled “[Les journaux de bord du règne de Chéops au ouadi el-Jarf \(P. Jarf AF\)](#) », 2017. Please, look at Figure 4 of this article. You can find Akhet Khufu six times. *Moreover, let us stress that it is written “Khufu Akhet pyramid”*. The English translation is available amers.hypotheses.org. Many thanks to Pierre Tallet and AMeRS association for the document.

The papyri of Wadi al-Jarf had been discovered in 2013, as announced by [Rossella Lorenzi, Discovery New](#). In 2014, Tallet published « Des papyrus du temps de Chéops au ouadi el-Jarf. Bulletin de la Société Française d’Égyptologie) ». This article is available at Academia.edu. In this article, we can

find toponyms, for instance, Tura, , rendered by Tallet, as “Horizon de Chéops”.

In Figure 20 of Tallet’s article in [Academia](#), we can find the AKHET Khufu arranged as follow:

Khufu Akhet Pyramid as in the papyrus B of Wadi al-Jarf, Figure 20, Tallet, 2014.

Note that Akhet is written with the crested ibis, the ‘sieve’ (circle with a bar inside) and the ‘bread bun’, the small semicircle. We will further discuss these symbols.

Mastaba of Qar

Before the discovery of the Wadi al-Jarf papyri (Tallet, 2014, 2017, Tallet and Marouard, 2014, Lehner and Tallet, 2022), the name of the Khufu’s pyramid was known, for instance, from an inscription in the mastaba of Qar.

[From Chris Naunton web site \(2024\)](#): we find a slide from Naunton’s talk “showing one of the titles held by the official Qar and containing the name of the Great Pyramid, the ‘Horizon of Khufu’ which is written with a pyramid determinative sign.” Here we show a part of the slide:

Fig.2: Akhet in Qar’s inscription.

It is written: “Overseer of the town of the pyramid Akhet”, then it follows the Khufu’s cartouche. Note the crested ibis. To see the tomb, visit [DigitalEpygraphy, Museo Egizio Torino collaboration](#).

See also the [transcription](#), which is proposed at the web site. Akhet was written with the crested ibis.

In Simpson, 1976, we can find described the mastabas of Qar and Idu, G7101 and 7102. gizamedia.rc.fas.harvard.edu :

B 2 *Imy-r niwt ʕht-Hwfw sš' nswt hft hr imʕh(w) Kʕr*, “overseer of the pyramid city Akhet-Khufu, king’s letter scribe in the presence, the well provided Qar.”

“Mr. Ashraf Mohieddin, General Manager of Antiquities of the Pyramid, said that the restoration work in the tomb of Qar included mechanical cleaning of the entire tomb, strengthening the roof at the entrance, and filling the gaps in the upper part of the main hall walls. It is a rock-cut tomb dating to the Sixth Dynasty, the reign of King Pepi I. Qar was the overseer of the two pyramid towns of Khufu and Menkaure, the inspector of the wab (pure) priests of the pyramid of Khafre, and the tenant of the pyramid of Pepi I.” (<https://egymonuments.gov.eg/news/opening-of-the-tombs-of-edo-and-qar/>)

“As for the tomb of Idu, Mohieddin indicated that ... This rock-cut tomb dates to the reign of the Sixth Dynasty King Pepi I as well. Idu was the son of Qar. His titles were the tenant of the Pyramid of Pepi I, the overseer of the scribes, and the inspector of the wab (pure) priests of the pyramid of Khufu and Khafre.” (<https://egymonuments.gov.eg/news/opening-of-the-tombs-of-edo-and-qar/>)

However, before the Mastaba of Qar (Giza), we find the name of the pyramid, Akhet Khufu, in older tombs.

G 1208	Stone-Mastaba	Akhethetep and his wife Meritites	Prophet of Khufu, Overseer of the Pyramid of Khufu, Overseer of the expedition, etc.	Mid 5th Dynasty or later	Meritites II was possibly a daughter of Khufu
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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Giza_West_Field

Giza 1208, owner Akhethetep

Courtesy <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/ancientpeople/2328/full/> - « Owner of G 1208. Chapel entrance drum lintel inscribed for Meretites and Akhethetep, identified as [rx nswt wab nswt sHD Hmw-nTr xwfw jmj-r mSa jmj-r Axt-xwfw xrp jmjw sA] royal acquaintance, royal wab-priest, inspector of priests of Khufu, expedition leader, overseer of the pyramid of Khufu, director of members of a phyle; in situ in G 1208”. In the image of the chapel entrance, we can find the Khufu cartouche and the name of Akhethetep. We can also find the name of the pyramid, as in the following sketch.

Fig. 3 – The names of Khufu (cartouche) and Akhethetep, and the name of the pyramid.

Details given by Digital Giza: Owner of G 1208. “overseer of the pyramid of Khufu”. Note, from left to right, a pyramid, the Khufu’s cartouche, a circle over the crested ibis, the ibis, a semicircle and the Khufu’s cartouche. Many thanks to the project Digital Giza, which is providing a huge help for science and research. Here we are using details of images, for research purposes only.

G 1204	Stone-Mastaba	Akhethetep	Royal acquaintance, inspector of priests of the pyramid of Khufu , great one of the tens of Upper Egypt	Mid 5th Dynasty or later	Two wives appear in the tomb: Seshseshet and Khenti . A son named Khufuankh is mentioned.
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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Giza_West_Field

Giza 1204, owner Akhethetep

Courtesy <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/ancientpeople/2329/full/> (consider the second picture given by the link).

Fig. 4 – Pyramid, crested ibis and the Khufu cartouche.

G 1457	Mud brick mastaba	Nisutnefret	Secretary of the king, director of royal wab-priests, overseer of the pyramid of Khufu , etc.	5th dynasty	Nisutnefret's wife Peretim is mentioned on the false door.
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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Giza_West_Field

Nisutnefret (G 1457)

Courtesy <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/sites/393/full/> “Owner of G 1457. Chapel entrance drum lintel and false door (including upper lintel) inscribed for Nisutnefret, identified as [rx nswt Hrj-sStA n nswt xrp n wabw nswt jmj-r Axt-xwfw jmj-r wabt nswt Hm-nTr xwfw] royal acquaintance, secretary of the king, director of royal wab-priests, overseer of the pyramid of Khufu, overseer of the royal wabet, priest of khufu; in situ in G 1457. Fragments of lintel and drum lintel (37-1-7, 37-1-8) inscribed for Nisutnefret; found east of G 1457.”

Please consider the 19th picture from the top of the list given at the web site at the link given above, that is <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/sites/393/full/> , and you can find the hieroglyphs as sketched in the following figure.

Fig.5: Crested ibis, round circle ('sieve'), semicircle ('bread bun'), the 'elliptical land', the symbols of pyramid and city, and also the Khufu cartouche. Then, the symbol of the land could be linked to the city, to indicate the city area.

G 1673	Stone mastaba	Qednes	Elder of the judicial court of the pyramid of Khufu, secretary of judgements	Late 5th or 6th dynasty	Qednes' wife: Niankhathor
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[Wikipedia](#)

Qednes (G 1673)

Courtesy <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/sites/464/full/> , 48th picture from the top of the list.

Fig. 6: Pyramid, crested ibis, circle and semicircle, pyramid and Khufu cartouche.

In Der Manuelian's book

Der Manuelian's book, 2009, contains the description of the 'Mastabas of Nucleus Cemetery G2100'. In this book we can find excerpts from the second report written by Reisner and signed by Reisner and Lythgoe: Report of the Work of the Expedition of Harvard University and the Boston Museum of Fine Arts up to January 31, 1906. Among the excerpts we find told that the mastabas of Strip I were the tombs of "priests and officials and their families who lived in the "City of the Glory of Cheops" ("Glory of Cheops" is the name of the First Pyramid), and had under their care the Pyramid with its two temples, the maintenance of the offerings to Cheops, and the administration of the estates left by Cheops for the maintenance of the offerings and the government of the city itself. They are therefore to be dated to the period subsequent to the death of Cheops, and belong, as a matter of fact, mostly to the 5th dynasty. Strip II however contains part of the royal cemetery of Cheops (see below c. The Work after Jan. 28) and its mastabas are therefore of the 4th dynasty...". In a note of Der Manuelian's book, it is told that the current name is 'Horizon of Khufu'.

In [Wikipedia](#): “Some inscriptions in the chapels of the mastabas (like the pyramid, their burial chambers were usually bare of inscriptions) mention Khufu or his pyramid. For instance, an inscription of Mersyankh III states that "Her mother [is the] daughter of the King of Upper and Lower Egypt Khufu." Most often these references are part of a title, for example, Snnw-ka, "Chief of the Settlement and Overseer of the Pyramid City of Akhet-Khufu"[33] or Nykahap, "priest of Khufu who presides over the pyramid Akhet-Khufu".[34][35] Several tomb owners have a king's name as part of their own name (e.g. Chufudjedef, Chufuseneb, Merichufu). The earliest pharaoh alluded to in that manner at Giza is Snefru (Khufu's father).[36][37]”. [33] is Der Manuelian, 2009, [34] is Simpson, 1980, [35] is <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/ancientpeople/2486/full/>, [36] is Jánosi, 2002, and [37] Hassan, 1960.

Fig.7

In [35], we can find, in the image courtesy [Giza Digital](#) showing the false door of the tomb of Nikahep (in G 2352), the Khufu cartouche, the crested ibis with the bread bun and the symbol of the pyramid. Below, there is the ‘elliptical land’, that is Kikahep, priest of Khufu, presided over the area of the pyramid of Khufu.

Note

This work of mine can be considered also a supplementary material of my arXiv, [Two Egyptian Kings, Shepseskaf and Userkaf, and a solar eclipse \(2471 BC\)](#). My <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407> was also motivated by a recent arXiv of Giulio Magli, 2024, where he wrote “Khufu will indeed build his pyramid on the Giza plateau, in plain view from Heliopolis (the main theological centre of the cult of Ra), and will make an explicit reference to the sun cult with the spectacular hierophany occurring at Giza at the summer solstice re-creating the “solarized” version of the double mountain sign, Akhet ☀️”. Magli is referring to Lehner 1985. We will consider Lehner, 1985, here in a detailed discussion. The symbol used by Magli is Gardiner N27. **Gardiner N27 was not used in Akhet Khufu!**

Let us note that, in 2014, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1401.0508>, Magli wrote: “We actually do not know the way in which the name of the Khufu complex was written during Khufu's reign (the unique possible attestation comes from a re-used fragmentary relief where the pyramid's determinative is not present); the “double mountains plus sun” sign first appears during the 5th dynasty”. Magli did not provide any reference about the re-used fragmentary relief; Magli did not provide any reference about the fact that Gardiner N27 appeared during the fifth dynasty. **Today we have the Wadi el-Jarf papyri.** Note that in 2014, Tallet and Marouard published the pictures of the Wadi al-Jarf papyri with the name of the pyramid, Akhet Khufu, with crested ibis, sieve and bread bun. **Moreover, as we have here clearly shown, in Giza, several inscriptions contain the name of the pyramid written with the crested ibis! N27 does not exist in the Akhet Khufu!**

Akhet (hieroglyphs)

In the Qar's mastaba, Akhet, followed by the symbol of the pyramid, is written as:

It is the same manner of writing Akhet that we find in the Wadi al-Jarf papyri.

Let us consider the symbols given above. The symbol of the pyramid is evident. Then we have:

, the 'sieve' or 'placenta', kh, [Aa1](#).

Between the pyramid and the Ibis, there is the combination Aa1 + t (or Aa1 + X1): [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Branch_\(hieroglyph\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Branch_(hieroglyph))

As the value (kh)t, it is often complemented in a [hieroglyphic block](#) with *kh*—"sieve"),

and "t"—(bread bun).

The semicircle is the "bread bun". It is the alphabetic-t. It is also used for the feminine determinative.

Mark Lehner and his two symbols for 'horizon'

We have seen above, in Fig.1, how the name of the pyramid was written at the time of Khufu.

However, there is a further detail to discuss. Mark Lehner, in several editions of his book written before the discovery of the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, proposed the name of the pyramid as:

Actually, Lehner added a further symbol, , which is meaning island, horizon, desert, [N18](#).

Akhet Khufu is written, as clearly shown by the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, with the crested ibis and the block containing the 'sieve' and the 'bread bun'. Sign N18 is not present.

Gardiner N27 , has the meaning of horizon too.

Robert Bauval, 2013, available [Academia.edu](#), explained that, looking at sign N27 Mark Lehner in 1985 wrote: "[a] dramatic effect is created at sunset during the summer solstice as viewed, again, from the eastern niche of the Sphinx Temple. At this time, and from this vantage, the sun sets almost exactly midway between the Khufu and Khafre pyramids, thus construing the image of the Akhet, 'Horizon', hieroglyph on a scale of acres". Bauval continued explaining that, "a fatal flaw [exists] with this idea: the hieroglyphic sign of the 'sun disk between two mountains' did not exist when Khufu built his pyramid! And even if it did, it was not used in the writing of the name 'Akhet Khufu'. In 1997 Lehner did acknowledge this fact: *Khufu's pyramid was Akhet Khufu. Here, and in the Pyramid Texts, Akhet is written with the crested-ibis and elliptical land-sign, not with the hieroglyph of the sun disk between two mountains that was used later to write 'horizon'.*" (Bauval, 2013).

Bauval is also discussing the Magli's 'hierophany'.

Please consider Lehner's words in the Lehner's book: "Khufu's pyramid was Akhet Khufu. Here, and in the Pyramid Texts, *Akhet is written with the crested ibis and elliptical land-sign, not with the hieroglyph of the sun disk between two mountains that was used later to write 'horizon'*. As the place where the deceased becomes an akh, a suggested translation is 'Spirit' or 'Light Land'." (Lehner, The Complete Pyramids, 1997, reprinted 2001). *Let us stress that that, in the Wady al-Jarf papyri, the Akhet is written with the crested ibis, the sieve and the bread bun (Tallet, 2017). N18 is not present. In the Qar's inscription too, N18 is absent. The only case is in Fig. 5, but it could be linked to the city area.*

According to Bauval, 2013, Lehner's "mistake in interpretation of the name of the Great Pyramid is still found in recently published books". "Lehner [in his The Complete Pyramids, 1997, p. 29] did recognize that 'Akhet' - although erroneously translated as 'horizon' in many books - is written with the crested-ibis that also denotes the word Akh, meaning a 'spirit' who lives in the Duat (afterworld), the latter often written with a star in a circle" (Bauval, 2013).

Let us stress once more, that Lehner, 1997, mentions *the elliptical sign for 'land', but in the name of the pyramid as written in the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, this sign does not exist. Then, in the Akhet Khufu there is no sign referring to 'land' or 'horizon'*.

According to James P. Allen, who translated the Pyramid Texts, Akhet is "the 'Place of Becoming Akh'..." (Bauval, 2013). As previously told, Bauval, 2013, is also mentioning G. Magli (see <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407> for further discussion).

Akhet Ra

Lehner added the symbol N18 to Akhet Khufu, but this symbol was not present in the inscriptions of Qar's mastaba and in the Wadi al-Jarf papyri. N18 is present in the "Horizon of Re". In Sellers, 1992. "About 2473 BC we find sun temples built some miles to the South of Giza. Six rulers in the Fifth Dynasty built these great temples to the sun and named them such names as Pleasure of Re, Horizon of Re and Field of Re". Horizon of Ra is Akhet Ra. It is the sun temple of Menkauhor Kaiu, the seventh ruler of the Fifth Dynasty at the end of the 25th century BC or early in the 24th century BC.

Fig.8: The Akhet of Ra (Courtesy Wikipedia).

Crested ibis, sieve, bread bun and elliptic land. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Menkauhor_Kaiu . Note 11: "The last hieroglyph shown here is an approximation of the correct one which shows a squat obelisk on a flat base called a ben-ben." Then, from right to left, the temple of Akhet Ra.

	O24A U+13275	pedestal of sun temple	Ascend (<i>j'(r)</i>)
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	O25A U+13277	obelisk and pedestal of sun temple	determinative for Sun temples
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Courtesy https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Egyptian_hieroglyphs#A

In Hany, 2022, we find details about the Sun-Temple: of Menkauhor.

Here a screenshot from Hany's article:

The king has established a sun temple to the worship of the god Re, and it is called *3h.t-Hr* 'Horus's horizon'; with the determinative of a mastaba⁴⁸.

(Hany, 2022).

See the Figure 8 in Hany, 2022. Notes 47 and 48 are referring to Ahmed Fakhry, *Pharaonic Egypt*, p. 108, and Borchardt, *Das Grabdenkmal des Königs Ne-User-Re*, Leipzig, 1907, p. 132.

Hany, 2022, is also providing the texts which are mentioning the Sun-temple of Menkauhor. In Saqqara (5th Dynasty Mastabas) (screenshot from Hani's article):

In the Tomb of *R^c-nfr-m^c* ⁽⁴⁹⁾ *3h.t-R^c Mn-k3w-Hr* "The sun-temple of Menkauhor".

In the Tomb of *ntri-stw 3h.t-Hr Mn-k3w-Hr* "The pyramid and the sun-temple of Menkauhor"⁵⁰.

(Hany, 2022)

Reference : Mariette, *Les Mastabas de l'ancien empire*, fragment du dernier ouvrage de A. Mariette; publié d'après le manuscrit de l'auteur par G. Maspero, Paris, 1889, pages 283, 284, 384.

Page 284, in Mariette, 1889, <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k1525597h/f294.item>

In the figure above, there is the elliptical land-sign. The crested ibis in names from [Mariette's book, 1885](#), are:

v. Beckerath	2342-2322
Shaw	2375-2345
Dodson	2312-2282
Allen	2353-2323
Malek	2341-2311
Redford	2404-2374

Years BCE, Unas chronology, courtesy <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/unas/>

Unas

Unas was the ninth and last ruler of the Fifth Dynasty of Egypt during the Old Kingdom.

The web site <https://pyramidtextsonline.com/index.html>, allows us to read the “Pyramid Texts of Unas: Hieroglyphs and Inscriptions”. On the page, we have the possibility to “view all of the walls of the pyramid of Unas (also spelled as Unis or Wenis) that are inscribed with hieroglyphs. Clicking on any wall image will link you to a larger view of the walls to view the hieroglyphic texts in detail. The Pyramid Texts of Unas are significant because they are the first known instance of hieroglyphic inscriptions in a pharaoh's tomb and are the earliest and most complete form of the Pyramid Texts. These inscriptions are found on the walls of the corridor, antechamber, passage, and sarcophagus chamber of the pyramid.”

Among the Credited persons, given at this [web page](#), let us stress that the Pyramid Texts Online was created by Vincent Brown. The English version is by J.D. Degreef, based on Alexandre Piankoff and

Louis Speleer works. J.D. Degreef provided scans of the photographic plates, from photographs taken by L.F. Husson under the direction of Natacha Rambova for Piankoff's The Pyramid of Unas.

<https://pyramidtextsonline.com/sarcsouthh.html>, Sarcophagus South Wall Hieroglyphs, Utterances 213 – 219. Here we find the crested ibis as Spirit.

“O Osiris, this Unas comes indeed, weary of the Nine, an Imperishable Spirit, to reckon hearts, to take kas, to grant kas. ... He comes indeed, this Unas, weary of the Nine, an Imperishable spirit, he that bore more than you ...”. The spirit is represented by the ibis alone.

The web page <https://pyramidtextsonline.com/antesouthh.html> shows the Akh imperishable spirit, and also the Horakhty, where we have Horus, the Akhet, and, below them, the sign of the elliptical land.

Let us also observe also the west wall of the corridor, thanks to the following link:

<https://pyramidtextsonline.com/corridorwesth.html>. Here, the word is present three times, in an ‘horizon’, according to the translation proposed by the web site.

Hieroglyphs

Then, let us propose a list.

a) sun-temple ‘Horizon of Re’, where the ‘horizon’ is

b) the symbols with the crested ibis in Unas' tomb: Akh, horizon, and Horakhty.

c) Khufu's pyramid, as written by Lehner, 2001:

d) Qar's mastaba, the name of the Khufu's pyramid is

e) Wadi al-Jarf Papyri, of Khufu's time:

Symbols in Akhet Khufu: pyramid, crested ibis, , Aa1 + t (or Aa1 + X1) : [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Branch_\(hieroglyph\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Branch_(hieroglyph))

The semicircle is the “bread bun”. It is the alphabetic-t. It is also used for the feminine determinative.

Horus of the Horizon (Horakhty)

Pyramid of Unas - Utterance 263 - 337. “The two Reed Floats of the sky are laid down for Re, that he may cross to the Horizon. The two Reed Floats of the sky are laid down for Horakhty, that **Horakhty** may cross on them to Re. The two Reed Floats of the sky are laid down for Unas, that he may cross on them to Horakhty, to Re”. Screenshot and translation, courtesy <https://pyramidtextsonline.com/antesouth.html>

“SOUTH WALL The king is identified with lightning (§§324 ff.) and stands on the eastern side of heaven. Two reed floats are placed for him as for Re and for **Horus of the Horizon** (§§337 ff.); he ascends on the smoke of incense (§365); he flies as a goose and alights on the seat of Re in the solar barge (§366). The ferryman of heaven is invoked; he has to transport the king as he does the gods (§§383 ff.). The king is he who inundates the earth like the Nile and brings prosperity to the living (§388).” (Piankoff, 1968). Piankoff uses the term ‘Horus of the Horizon’.

Fig. 9 - The screenshot is here used to stress that the Horus of the Horizon is truly present in the Unas’ utterance.

The two reed floats of the sky are laid down for Re
that he may cross to the horizon.

The two reed floats of the sky are laid down for **Horus of the Horizon**,
that **Horus of the Horizon** may cross on them to Re.

The two reed floats of the sky are laid down for Unas,
that he may cross on them to **Horus of the Horizon**, to Re.

(Piankoff, 1968)

“Horus, in ancient Egyptian religion, a god in the form of a falcon whose right eye was the sun or morning star, representing power and quintessence, and whose left eye was the moon or evening star, representing healing. Falcon cults, which were in evidence from late predynastic times, were widespread in Egypt.” <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Horus>

“The sky’s two reed floats have been set for the Sun, that he might cross on them to the Akhet; the sky’s two reed floats have been set for **Horus of the Akhet**, that Horus of the Akhet might cross on them to where the Sun is; the sky’s two reed floats have been set for Unis, that he might cross on them to the Akhet, where the Sun is: the sky’s two reed floats have been set for Unis, that he might cross on them to where Horus of the Akhet is, to where the Sun is.” (Allen, 2007).

Akhethetep (fifth dynasty)

Akhethetep (c. 2400 BC) was a high dignitary who lived during the fifth dynasty. Akhethetep and his son Ptahhotep Tjefi were officials during the rule of Djedkare and of Unas, towards the end of the fifth dynasty. “Akhethetep's titles included that of a vizier” ([Wikipedia](#)). “He is famous for [his tomb](#), discovered in Saqqara” (Wikipedia).

In de Garis Davies and Griffith, 1900, we can find the decorations and inscriptions of the Mastaba of Ptahhetep and Akhethetep, https://dlib.nyu.edu/ancientworld/books/ifa_egypt000220/1

Fig.10: The name of Akhethetep from Davies and Griffith, 1900. Note the ibis and the bread bun.

“One can notice a trend towards the end of the Fifth Dynasty, perhaps starting with Menkauhor’s reign, to bear names formed with that of a deity other than Re. Names such as Ptahetep, Akhethetep, Sebekhetep, etc. became particularly popular in this period” (Kanawati, 2003).

“Hotep (ḥtp; also rendered hetep) is an Egyptian word that roughly translates as "to be satisfied, at peace". The word also refers to an "offering" ritually presented to a deity or a dead person, hence "be pleased, be gracious, be at peace". It is rendered in Egyptian hieroglyphs as an altar (Gardiner sign R4). The noun ḥtp.w means "peace, contentment". Davies (2018) interprets the concept of ḥtp as "the result of action in accord with maat [the proper order of the universe]" ([Wikipedia](#)).

Akhethetep is a “be the Spirit fulfilled”. No elliptic sign N18 for the horizon. No Aa1 sign, “sieve”. But there is the bread bun.

The translation

Creighton, 2014: “Lehner was *probably one of the first academics* to recognize the translation problem that these two quite distinct versions of the word akhet present. In Lehner’s view the older term akhet, with the crested ibis, should not be translated as ‘horizon’ at all but instead is to be associated with the ‘**Spirit of Khufu**’. Lehner writes, ‘joining the stars, the king becomes an akh, [and] Akh is often translated as ‘spirit’ or ‘spirit state’. It derives from the term for ‘radiant light’, written with the crested ibis ... Akh is also the word for ‘effective’, ‘profitable’, ‘useful’” (Creighton, 2014). *As we will see in our discussion, Schiaparelli, 1892, had already proposed to translate the Akhet as “spirit”. Therefore, the problem of the translation of Akhet was quite old, as detailed by Kuentz, 1920.*

Fig.11: The pyramid Akhet Khufu in Wadi el-Jarf papyri, as given in the [picture](#) of the article “Records of the pyramid builders: discovering eye-witness accounts of a legendary construction project”, [The Past.](#), 2023. The transcription is given according to Tallet, 2017.

In Kuentz, 1920, we can find that the ibis sign in Akhet was used by Pepi II in a letter to his vizier Herkhuf (Harkhuf):

Tu as dit en cette tienne missive que tu amenais de la Terre des Horizontaux un Deng dansant le dieu, semblable au Deng que le scelleur de dieu Ba-our-zeded amena de Pount au temps d'Asesi.

Note the signs, for the horizon and it the dwellers, and the three divinities:

Herkhuf (or Harkhuf) visited the land of the Horizon dwellers (Goedicke, 1981, Bauval, & Brophy, 2011). Herkhuf, was a governor of Aswan, who journeyed extensively throughout Nubia.

“As attested by his tomb biography, Harkhuf, a native of Elephantine, was appointed governor of the southern part of Upper Egypt and overseer of caravans under King Merenre, third king of the 6th dynasty. His primary business, however, was trade with Nubia. His first journey originated from Memphis, near modern Cairo; its destination was either the Second Nile Cataract region or beyond, and it entailed seven months’ travel. A second journey passed uneventfully. On the third trip, Harkhuf found the nation at war with a Libyan tribe. As part of his duty was to keep trade routes open, he persuaded the warring chief to desist from strife. Following an exchange of goods, Harkhuf returned with 300 asses laden with incense, ebony, skins, and ivory; an armed escort guided him through the territory of the potentially dangerous tribal coalition. Under Pepi II, fourth king of the 6th dynasty,

Harkhuf traveled south again and brought back a Pygmy from inner Africa. The young king was delighted and sent a letter to Harkhuf, which was reproduced in his tomb”, according to information in <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Harkhuf>

« Le premier éditeur et premier traducteur E. Schiaparelli, en 1892, comprit naturellement «la Terra degli Spiriti beati » - Rendant compte de l’ouvrage de Schiaparelli, G. Maspero ne modifia pas cette traduction : «Terre des Mânes·», «Terre des Esprits » ... De là des commentaires curieux : «(Le nain) de Hirkhouf passait pour être originaire de la Terre des Esprits. La Terre des Esprits n’est pas une région déterminée, c’est un terme emprunté aux croyance populaires de l’Égypte et répondant au même ordre d’idées qu’exprime ... » (Kuentz, 1920).

Here are screenshots from Schiaparelli, 1892.

Please note the Glory

<https://digi.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/diglit/schiaparelli1892>

“Da quanto è detto nel rescritto del Faraone in onore di Hirkhuf, si deve inferire che il risultato che parve più notevole del suo secondo viaggio fu l'aver portato in Egitto: « un Donka che ballava divinamente, dalla Terra degli spiriti beati ».” (Schiaparelli, 1892). “Bensì Hirkhuf pervenne ad una regione, che egli designa col nome di “Terra degli spiriti beati” o « degli spiriti luminosi », che alle sedi dei Pigmei doveva trovarsi abbastanza vicina perché alcuni individui di quelle tribù vi si potessero trovare nelle medesime circostanze di quelli ... Sulla posizione della « Terra degli spiriti beati » nulla dice l'iscrizione di Hirkhuf, dalla quale può soltanto inferirsi che si trovasse al sud, ...” (Schiaparelli, 1892).

We can see the letter from Pepi II to Herkhuf in Schiaparelli’s pictures.

Fig.12: Thanks to the the [Museo Egizio di Torino](#), Museo Egizio di Torino, we can see the original text. The images are provided Under CC0 license. The panel (up) shows a detail of Photo 10/27, Schiaparelli excavations, Year, 1914, Plate C01547. The panel (down) is a detail of Plate C01548. Caption of Photos 10/11/27 is: “Right wall of the façade of the tomb of Herkhuf (QH34n). The text is a letter from the young Pharaoh Pepi II, in which Herkhuf is honored for his expedition, from where he brought back a pygmy”.

In Gautschy et al., the chronology of Pepi II, is the following:

1 Pepi II	2201 BCE	2216 BCE	2278 BCE	2279/2229	---	2334 BCE
				BCE		

Pepi II is of the sixth dynasty. We can see the crested ibis and the elliptical land sign for horizon.

Then, when N27 has been introduced for “horizon”?

Creighton, 2014, notes that “the akhet pictogram for “horizon” (believed to depict the sun rising between two mountains) did not actually exist when Khufu was building his Great Pyramid, ..., this pictogram only came into being around the end of the Fifth Dynasty, long after Khufu and the completion of the early, giant pyramids” (Creighton, 2014). No reference given by Creighton about the introduction of the N27 symbol at the end of the Fifth Dynasty. The burden of proof is with Creighton. According to the Letter of Pepi II, we can find that the crested ibis for ‘horizon’ was used even three centuries after Khufu.

Pepi II used the crested ibis, not the sun disk on the land.

Fig.13 - Courtesy [Wikipedia, Wadi Hammamat](#)

“One of the earliest pieces of evidence of the use or exploitation of the Wadi Hammamat may be a graffito containing a serekh of the Early Dynastic King Narmer, which is inscribed on a rock in the Wadi el-Qash, an offshoot of the Wadi Hammamat. ... It seems to be Nebhepetre Mentuhotep II of Dynasty XI who re-opened the Wadi Hammamat route and possibly sent quarrying expeditions there at the beginning of the Middle Kingdom and a short hieroglyphic graffito most probably dates to his rule” ([egyptsites.wordpress.com](#))

Mentuhotep II

He was the **fifth pharaoh of the Eleventh Dynasty** (v. Beckerath 2046–1995). “Mentuhotep II reigned for 51 years, but after 14 years of peace and prosperity, the Heracleopolitan tenth dynasty desecrated the Abydos necropolis, effectively starting a war with the pharaoh of Thebes. During the next twenty years the conflict raged on, neither side winning outright. Sometime during this time, Mentuhotep changed his names, perhaps to reflect the ambition to reunite the Two Lands. After finally accomplishing the defeat of the Heracleopolitans, the Two Lands were once again united under a pharaoh, and once again, his names were changed to reflect this.” <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/mentuhotep-ii/>

« A la suite d’une importante expédition envoyée au Ouâdi Hammâmât pour y extraire un bloc de belle pierre destinée à son sarcophage, le roi Mentouhotep II fit graver sur une paroi de rocher, — par les soins du chef des travaux, le vizir Amen-em-hait, — une inscription commémorative dont le texte suit. Elle se compose de deux lignes horizontales (date et protocole) et de dix-neuf colonnes verticales; les trois dernières colonnes forment une sorte d’appendice, elles ont du être gravées après coup, car un certain espace et un double trait vertical de séparation sont ménagés entre les colonnes 18 et 19. Le corps même de l’inscription comprend trois longues phrases constituant trois parties :

motif de l'érection de la stèle, objet de l'expédition, conclusion reprenant la première partie (17-18). L'appendice relate la fin des travaux et leurs résultats. » (Kuentz, 1920).

« Sa Majesté a ordonné d'ériger la présente stèle à son père Min, le maître des contrées montagneuses, sur ce mont-ci : mont vénérable, primordial, premier de place dans

palais du dieu, doué de la vie d'Horus, nid divin où prospère ce dieu, sa place sacrée de divertissement qui est à la tête des montagnes de la Terre du Dieu ... » (Kuentz, 1920)

The expression requires attention. A possible translation is the Land of the Horizon. Kuentz arrives to the translation: « pays des habitants de l'horizon », « des Horizontaux ». « Cette expression curieuse désigne, avons-nous vu, toute la contrée dont la Vallée de Rohanou et nous rappelons un seul autre texte qui permette un rapprochement ... c'est un texte d'Ancien Empire, provenant du tombeau de Ibsouan. Mais ceci réclame une discussion spéciale, ... », then Kuentz started discussing the Letter of Pepi II.

It seems that between Pepi the Second and Mentuhopet II, the sign of the sun disk on the land had been introduced.

Schiaparelli and the Herkhuf's report to Pepi II. Note the symbol with the three 'mountains'.

The mountains and the crested ibis (Abydos)

In Kuentz, and also in the pictures made by Schiaparelli, we can find the sign of the “three hills” (Herkhuf reports to Pepi II and Pepi II letter).

Fig.14

A detail from Herkhuf's tomb. <https://archiviofotografico.museoegizio.it/en/archive/aswan/qubbet-el-hawa/tomb-qh-34-n-herkhuf/?photo=C01543>

Kuentz (or KÜNTZ) is mentioned in an article by Jean–Pierre PÄTZNICK, entitled « L'Éléphant sur le Signe des Trois Collines et Hiérakonpolis », 2020. We find a discussion of a very old egyptian sign: that of the three hills. However, in a tomb of Abydos, also the crested ibis had been found on a tag, a tomb of the Egypt that existed before the Pyramids.

« Vers la fin de la Dynastie 0 (Nagada III A2), on trouve aussi l'iconogramme aux trois et quatre collines associé à un animal. Sur certaines des étiquettes du Tombeau Uj à Abydos, il se trouve alors en relation avec l'éléphant, les serpents et les ibis tandis que du début au milieu de la Ie Dynastie, le signe aux trois ou quatre collines est uniquement associé à des mammifères (éléphant, buffle, lycan / hyène). Au vu de ces composites, on peut dès lors suggérer que ces deux catégories d'iconogrammes devaient revêtir la fonction d'un déterminatif, d'un sémiogramme, caractérisant un territoire placé sous la protection d'une entité animale. Partant de ce constat, l'attention peut dès lors se porter sur le groupe [éléphant aux trois collines]. En l'absence de signes phonétiques complémentaires, le signe composite pose de prime abord un problème de lecture et de compréhension. » (Pätznick, 2020).

« Ces découvertes et observations associées à d'autres exemples connus d'animaux figurant au-dessus du signe hiéroglyphique N25 des trois collines, tels que le taureau et le lion observés sur les Colosses de Coptos et l'Ibis comata et les serpents sur les étiquettes en ivoire recueillies dans la Tombe Uj à Abydos par l'équipe de G. Dreyer (DAI, Le Caire) invitent à les comparer aux graphies de nomes utilisant le groupe ANIMAL + N25, comme celles du 6e Nome de Basse-Égypte ou des 10e et 12e Nomes de Haute Égypte » (Pätznick, 2020).

L'oiseau Ax (G25), identifié à l'**Ibis comata**, [crested ibis], est associé à l'iconogramme des trois ou quatre collines » and Pätznick, 2020, mentions in a note : « Planche II, Fig. 2. Voir DREYER et al. 1998A: 130, Fig. 133-34 & Pl. 33 (mêmes figures). » « Sur une des étiquettes, l'ibis est même représenté, décentré, les pattes sur deux des quatre sommets du signe. Cette association de l'oiseau et de la montagne fait curieusement écho au Pays des Axytyw, comme semble avoir été nommée une lointaine région de Nubie à l'Ancien Empire », and Pätznick, 2020, mentions Kuentz.

Pätznick, 2020, refers to the tags in Dreyer, 1998. See Mitchell, 1999, about the earliest hieroglyphs. We can find them also in Wegner, 2007, in an article entitled "From elephant-mountain to Anubis-mountain? A theory on the origins and development of the name Abdu", available [Academia.edu](https://www.academia.edu).

"On the one hand, while reading the combination of elephant + mountain sign as a royal name, Dreyer also posits that the two signs function together as hieroglyphs with phonetic value as a writing of the toponym Ab-Dw, "Elephant Mountain." This is one of a group of sign combinations on the U-j tags which he argued can be taken as toponyms. Two others understandable in this way are the combination of stork and seat as a writing for 'Basta', and ibis atop a façade as a writing for 'Buto' (Dreyer 1998: 139). Dreyer noted that the mode in which the desert-hills symbol is employed on other

tags suggests it can occur with phonetic value. Particularly, where it occurs in combination with the *d*-snake symbol both double and triple-peaked mountain signs appear to have the value of *dw* (see Dreyer 1998: 143 and Taf. 33). If it is being used in this way, it appears quite viable that the combination of elephant + triple peaked mountain sign in the Tomb U-j tags can be understood as an archaic writing for *Abdw*: Abydos” (Wegner, 2007).

Fig.15

“Fragment with the cartouche of Akhenaten New Kingdom, Amarna Period”, in an image courtesy The MET. Credit: Harris Brisbane Dick Fund, 1957.

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/567657>

From Abydos to Akhetaten

“Amenhotep IV reigned for five years before changing his name to Akhenaten, keeping only the throne name of his original titular. He is especially famed for introducing the worship of Aten above all other gods, sometimes described as monotheism, which it was not”. <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/amenhotep-iv/>

He was tenth pharaoh of the Eighteenth Dynasty.

Courtesy <https://pharaoh.se/ancient-egypt/pharaoh/amenhotep-iv/>

We have already seen in Schiaparelli . The name Akhenaten means “The Glory of Aten”.

From <https://www.ancientegyptblog.com/?p=2038> : the cartouche of Akhenaten can be read as

 - Of (pronounced like “n”). “Spirit of the Aten.” Or, using Schiaparelli, the Glory of Aten.

Then, in the name Akhenaten, we have the crested ibis, the disk for “sieve” or “placenta”, but not the “bread bun”, which is representing the sound “t”, because we have the wavelets giving sound “n”.

Regarding Amarna, the Akhenaten's capital, in <https://www.ancientegyptblog.com/?p=1320> we find told: "Amarna as it is commonly called, is the modern name for Akhetaten ☉⏏⏏⏏⏏⊗." Akhetaten is therefore written as:

"**Akhetaten** means 'Horizon of the Sun Disc': the mountain sign is the horizon. (Akhet) and the signs to the right spell Aten (the sun)." https://www.arch.cam.ac.uk/files/amarna_english_introduction.pdf

At the time of the reign of Akhenaten, it existed ☉⏏, the Horizon of the SUN DISK! We can see the king's cartouche and the name of the Akhetaten city on one of the "Boundary Stelae of Akhenaten", that known as Stele S, for instance. "The boundary stelae of Akhenaten are unique in the surviving record. Among the oldest recorded statements at the foundation of a city, they take the form of rock inscriptions in the cliffs around Akhetaten 'the horizon of the Aten'. Akhetaten is the city founded by king Akhenaten (reigned about 1351-1334 BC) in the desert bay in Middle Egypt halfway between ancient Memphis and Thebes. The inscriptions are the first kingship monuments written mainly in Late Egyptian, closer to the spoken language of New Kingdom Egypt (1550-1070 BC) than the courtly and more formal Middle Egyptian from the Middle Kingdom (2025-1700 BC). This modernization of written language would have created a strong impact on the ancient reader. The contents are also radical; they present the city as a monument made by the king for the only god he worshipped, the sun-god Ra in his most visible form, the sun-disk (in Egyptian: Aten). This marks the greatest upheaval in the religious history of ancient Egypt, and is often labelled the first recorded instance of monotheism (exclusive belief in one god)" (<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/amarna/boundary.html>, archived).

"Jean Daressy published the earliest printed translation of the legible parts of the text, also in 1893, based on copies of stelae S and R, using variants found on stelae A and U" (Wikipedia, mentioning Murnane and Van Siceln III, 2012). Here in the following image a detail of the upper part of stele S.

Fig.16

Note the cartouches with the name Akhenaten, where Akhen is represented with the crested ibis. Note

also the Aten . This is a detail from the image proposed at the web page of [Wikipedia Italia](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boundary_Stelae_of_Akhenaten#/media/File:Amarna_boundary_stela_U_01.JPG). The web page contains a reproduction of Plate XIII, « Monuments Egyptiens, bas-reliefs, peintures, inscriptions, etc. », Prisse d'Avennes.

Fig. 17-Details of the Boundary stela U, Amarna, Egypt. Courtesy Einsamer Schütze for Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boundary_Stelae_of_Akhenaten#/media/File:Amarna_boundary_stela_U_01.JPG

Solstices

“In regnal year eight, this heretical Pharaoh moved the capital into the middle part of Egypt near the modern site of Tell-el-Amarna where the Sun disc, Aton, was elevated to the status of the only true god. The capital was filled with Sun-inspired art of a new style. The king called his new capital Akhetaton, “the Horizon of Aton”. When he erected his own tomb at Tell-elAmama, all rooms and corridors leading up to the burial chamber, in violation of a tradition of his forebears and successors, were along a single axis from south-east to north-west (a Sun rising direction at the solstices).” (Gurshtein, 1997).

No reference is given by Gurshtein about the direction of corridors in the Akhenaten’s tomb. Strictly necessary to control. This is true in any case, even when citations are given.

Ra-Horakhty (New Kingdom)

Fig.18

Stele dedicata da Smen a Ra-Horakhty, Nr. inv.: Cat. 1648, Datazione: 1292–1190 a.C. Periodo: Nuovo Regno. XIX dinastia. Provenienza: Deir el-Medina. Bernardino Drovetti, 1824.

Courtesy: [Museo Egizio Torino](#).

Fig.19

Stele dedicata al dio Ra-Harakhty da parte dello scultore Ipy, Nr. inv.: Cat. 7357, Datazione: 1292–1190 a.C. Periodo: Nuovo Regno, Dinastia: XIX dinastia, Provenienza: Deir el-Medina, Bernardino Drovetti, 1824

Courtesy: [Museo Egizio Torino](#)

Fig.20

Note please how (Ra)-Horakhty is written during the New Kingdom. Of course, it is different from the Horakhty of Unas pyramid.

HARMACHIS

This name from 'Har-em-akhet' or 'Horus in the horizon' aptly regionalises Horus as sun-god. Pharaonic inscriptions of the New Kingdom reinterpreted the sphinx at Giza, originally representing King Khafra guarding the approach to his pyramid, as Harmachis looking towards the eastern horizon (see also HAURUN).

From The Routledge dictionary of Egyptian gods and goddesses, Hart, 2005.

In Shaw, 2015, we can find told that, "from at least as early as the Middle Kingdom, the Egyptians recognized five of the planets". We find "Jupiter (Horus who limits the two lands), Mars (Horus of the horizon or Horus the red)", and so on.

Mentioning C. Fagan, Gurshtein tells, "He [Fagan] stated that from 3 130 B.C., in archaic Egypt, there was a calendrical era founded on the heliacal rising of the planet Mars, which was known under a name "Horus of the Horizon" (later on it became "Horus the Red"). This calendrical era was the Harakhte Era, the word Harakhte being the Greek translation of the Egyptian Hor-akhti which literally means "Horus of the Horizon". This time the observers could not perform the measurements on the starry dome of the sky and they were limited by the measurements along the line of the horizon only. Systematical observations of luminaries' risings and settings took place, partially in comparison with each other, and one may identify this time as a period of the astronomy on the horizon. As a result of the long systematical astronomical observations, an occasional coincidence of Sirius (in the Egyptian - spit, or Sothis) heliacal rising with the Nile flooding was discovered. It seems to be Imhotep who created a new calendrical system and simultaneously introduced the Sothic Era, ca. 2767 B.C., as mentioned above. C. Fagan insists that modern scholars are absolutely wrong in their understanding of the ancient meaning of the term horoscope. ..." (Gurshtein, 1997).

Once more, no reference given by Gurshtein. Strictly necessary to control.

Note

Belmonte and Magli mentioned the Wadi al-Jarf papyri in 2015, in "[the global project of Sneferu at Dahshur](#)". In this 2015 paper, Belmonte and Magli are proposing again the idea proposed years before, that the two largest pyramids at Giza were planned in a single project by Khufu. Referring to "The harbour of Khufu on the Red Sea coast at Wadi al-Jarf, Egypt", Near Eastern Archaeology, Belmonte and Magli tell that Tallet and Marouard "have found a papyrus, contemporaneous to Cheops's reign, with a text where Axt xfw is mentioned with a single determinative of a pyramid (as in later sources). This, according to José Lull (private communication), would be a point against the duality of the complex" (Belmonte and Magli, 2015). Therefore, Magli and Belmonte know the Wadi al-Jarf papyri, but they continue to link Khufu to N27, the 'solarized' horizon. Moreover, they did not provide references about the 'later sources'.

The idea of Belmonte and Magli is that Khufu planned also the second pyramid in Giza, that of Khafre, to create the hieroglyphs of the horizon, as in N27, and the Sphinx between the pyramids.

See please my <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.20407>, for the observations given by Bauval, 2013. Bauval stressed, about Magli's proposal of two pyramids planned by Khufu, that the sign N27 was NOT used in the name of the pyramid, Akhet Khufu. Bauval was right.

Between Khufu and Khafre there was another king. There was Djedefre. And he built his pyramid at Abu Rawash.

Returning to Belmonte and Magli, [2015, archived](#), look please at their Figure 9. They insist on the Khufu's project. In panel (a), Akhet Khufu is badly written: the order of terms is wrong, such as the Khufu's cartouche. In panel (b), they propose "a symbolic reinterpretation as the god Hor-em-akhet, 'Horus at the Horizon', during the New Kingdom" (Belmonte and Magli, 2015). They put the falcon G5, Horus, inside N27. In the caption (b) of Figure 9, Belmonte and Magli state that, in the New Kingdom, this was the representation of 'Horus at the Horizon'. As shown in the images given above, the falcon Horu is outside N27, which has a shape different from that given in the Gardiner's list. Of course, it is very different from the 'Horus at the Horizon' given in Unas pyramid.

Since Belmonte and Magli, 2015, do not provide any reference to the symbol they show in the panel (b) of their Figure 9, the symbol that they show has no evidential value.

The caption of Fig.9 by Belmonte and Magli tells "Architecture and astral symbolism at Giza as initially recreated in the Old Kingdom (a) with the **hypothetical** two-pyramid plus Sphinx project of Cheops, or Axt xfw, 'Khufu's Horizon', and (b) ...". It has been already said that Akhet Khufu is written in a wrong manner. Let us stress once more that Akhet Khufu is the 'Spirit of Khufu', as Lehner recognized after revising translation of Akhet. Moreover, the **Khafre pyramid has its own name. Then, to put the name of one of the two pyramids between them is misleading.**

Fig. 4. **Crested ibis** (species ?), . M.W.B., 1891.

The bird is highly conventionalized.

The sign is used to spell the root *akh*, which occurs with the meanings: (1) "brilliant," also "excellent," "useful"; (2) the glorified spirit of man after death. As in the case of the *ba* (Fig. 3), this spirit also was perhaps considered to exist in a bird form.

Griffith, 1896.

Conclusion: Akhet Khufu, the Enduring Forever Glory of Khufu.

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